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Unlocking the secrets of Albania's endangered butterfly populations: a comprehensive review of Red Lists and strategic approaches for enhancing conservation efforts to better target species and priority areas.

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Abstract

This paper explores the significant evolution of three Red Lists for the Papilionoidea in Albania (2006, 2013, and 2022) in comparison to the latest status of the Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas (09.i.2025).

This marked evolution underscores the need for effective species monitoring that minimizes bias and maximizes both the quantity and quality of data collected, moving beyond sole reliance on opportunistic field research by entomologists and biodiversity repositories such as Inaturalist and Observado. This need is particularly relevant as Albania rapidly develops into a Western-style, economically driven country, facing threats akin to those seen in new EU member states in past decades, which have experienced significant declines in butterfly populations and distribution. Providing standardized and regularly updated status indicators is essential for guiding conservation efforts, enabling swift adaptation to emerging challenges in protecting endangered butterflies and their habitats.

Key words

Red List, Papilionoidea, butterflies, Albania, biodiversity, conservation efforts optimization.

Introduction

The International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of threatened species (IUCN) is a vital resource used not only by scientists but also by anyone concerned with nature and biodiversity, to evaluate the conservation status of species. By categorizing species according to their risk of extinction, the Red List plays a pivotal role in guiding global conservation policies and raising awareness about the ongoing loss of biodiversity. Through a thorough scientific evaluation that considers factors such as population size, habitat loss, and various threats, this invaluable tool provides a voice for the species most in urgent need of protection.

In accordance with the national legal framework, the first national Red List of Albania was compiled and published in 2006 in a separate Red Book of Albanian flora and [Red Book of Albanian fauna](#).

In the 2006 edition of Albania's threatened insect classification, a total of 125 species were assessed. Among them, 7 species were categorized as Critically Endangered (CR), 5 as Endangered (EN), 89 as Vulnerable (VU), 18 as Least Concern (LC), and 6 as Data Deficient (DD). Notably, 70 of these species belong to the order Lepidoptera, including 55 classified as Vulnerable, 3 as Critically Endangered, and 2 as Endangered.

Five years later, in 2012, the revision and update of Albania's first Red List began and was completed in 2013. The classification of species in the Albanian Red List followed the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. The updated national Red List was officially approved in December 2013 by Ministerial Order No. 1280, dated 20.11.2013.

The updated 2013 Red List includes 107 species from the class Insecta, with 63 belonging to the order Lepidoptera. Among them, 2 species are classified as Endangered (EN) and 3 as Critically Endangered (CR).

Building on the extensive fieldwork conducted over the past decade and the annually updated [Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas](#) (09.ii.2025), a new online version of the Red List was launched in 2022. This version places the [Red List 2022](#) in the context of the [European Red List](#) (2010), the [Mediterranean Red List](#) (2016), the [Habitat Directives](#), and provides valuable information on declining, disjunct, and range-limited populations ([Supplementary Material](#)).

A few years later, with a significant increase in observational data, it became relevant to assess how current the [Red List 2022](#) remains and to optimize future targeting of species and areas for conservation efforts.

Discussion

A qualitative comparison of Albania's three Butterfly Red Lists is presented (Table 1), integrating new insights from recent field surveys conducted since the publication of the [Red List 2022](#). The nomenclature is based on [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025) and was adapted accordingly hereunder for the three Red Lists.

Heteropterus morpheus (Pallas, 1771) was added to the [Red List 2022](#) after being recorded ([source](#)) in 2023 from a single locality.

Pelopidas thrax (Hübner, [1821]) a butterfly in expansion ([source](#)), was added to the [Red List 2022](#) after its first recorded sightings in 2024.

Table 1. Comparison of the Albanian Butterfly Red Lists of 2006, 2013 and 2022. Notes (1 to 8) are discussed below Table 1.

Papilionidae	Red List (2006)	Red List (2013)	Red List (2022)	Note	Proposed status
Papilioninae					
<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			LC		
<i>Papilio alexanor</i> Esper, [1800]	VU (B2b)	VU B2b	VU B2b		
<i>Papilio machaon</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			LC		
Parnassiinae					
<i>Allanacstria cerisyi</i> (Godart, 1823)	VU (A1b, B2a)		NT		
<i>Driopa mnemosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU	VU	NT	1	LC
<i>Parnassius apollo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	CR	CR	NT	1	LC
<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> [(Denis & Schiffermüller), 1775]	VU (A1b)	VU B2a	VU B2a		
Hesperiidae					
Hesperiinae					
<i>Gegenes nostradamus</i> (Fabricius, 1793)			NT		
<i>Gegenes pumilio</i> (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804)	LRnt	LRnt	NT		
<i>Hesperia comma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU		NE		
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i> (Esper, 1777)			NE		
<i>Pelopidas thrax</i> (Hübner, [1821])			NE	2	NE
<i>Thymelicus acteon</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	NT		
<i>Thymelicus lineola</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)			NE		
<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i> (Poda, 1761)			NE		
Heteropterinae					
<i>Carterocephalus palaemon</i> (Pallas, 1771)			NE	3	VU
<i>Heteropterus morpheus</i> (Pallas, 1771)			VU		
Pyrginae					
<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, [1780])	VU (A1b)	VU	LC	5	LC
<i>Erynnis marloyi</i> (Boisduval, [1834])	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Erynnis tages</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC	5	LC
<i>Muschampia floccifera</i> (Zeller, 1847)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Muschampia lavatherae</i> (Esper, [1783])			VU		
<i>Muschampia orientalis</i> (Reverdin, 1913)			NE		
<i>Muschampia alta</i> (Schwingenschuss, 1942)			NE		
<i>Pyrgus alveus</i> (Hübner, [1803])			NE		
<i>Pyrgus andromedae</i> (Wallengren, 1853)			NE	3	VU
<i>Pyrgus armoricanus</i> (Oberthür, 1910)	EN (A1b)	EN	LC		

	Red List (2006)	Red List (2013)	Red List (2022)	Note	Proposed status
<i>Pyrgus carthami</i> (Hübner, [1813])			NE		
<i>Pyrgus cinarae</i> (Rambur, [1839])			NE		
<i>Pyrgus malvae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Pyrgus serratulae</i> (Rambur, [1839])			NE		
<i>Pyrgus sidae</i> (Esper, [1784])			LRnt		
<i>Spialia orbifer</i> (Hübner, [1823])	LRnt	LRnt	NE	7	LC
<i>Spialia phlomidis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845])	DD		NE	6	DD
Pieridae					
Coliadinae					
<i>Colias alfacariensis</i> Ribbe, 1905	VU (B2a)	VU(B2a)	LC		
<i>Colias aurorina</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1850]			NT		
<i>Colias caucasica</i> Staudinger, 1871			EN		
<i>Colias croceus</i> (Geoffrey, 1785)			NE	7	LC
<i>Gonepteryx cleopatra</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	LRnt	LRnt	NT		
<i>Gonepteryx farinosa</i> (Zeller, 1847)	LRnt	LR	NT		
<i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
Dismorphiinae					
<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	VU (B1)	VU B1	VU B1		
<i>Leptidea juvernica</i> Williams, 1946			DD		
<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
Pierinae					
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Anthocharis damone</i> Boisduval, 1836			NT		
<i>Anthocharis gruneri</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]	VU (B1)	VU B1	NT		
<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Euchloe ausonia</i> (Hübner, [1804])			NE		
<i>Euchloe penia</i> (Freyer, [1851])	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Pieris balcana</i> Lorković, [1969]			LC		
<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Pieris ergane</i> (Geyer, [1828])			NE	7	LC
<i>Pieris krueperi</i> Staudinger, 1860	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Pieris mannii</i> (Mayer, 1851)			NE	7	LC
<i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Pontia edusa</i> (Fabricius, 1777)			NE	7	LC
Lycaenidae					
Lycaeninae					
<i>Lycaena alciphron</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lycaena candens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Lycaena dispar</i> ([Haworth], 1802)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Lycaena ottomanus</i> (Lefebvre, 1831)	VU (A1b)	VU B2a	VU B2a		
<i>Lycaena phlaeas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lycaena thersamon</i> (Esper, [1784])			NE		
<i>Lycaena tityrus</i> (Poda, 1761)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lycaena virgaureae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	3	VU
Polyommatae					
<i>Aricia agestis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Aricia anteros</i> (Freyer, 1839)			LC		
<i>Aricia artaxerxes</i> (Fabricius, 1793)			NE		
<i>Cacyreus marshalli</i> Butler 1898			NE		
<i>Celastrina argiolus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Cupido alcetas</i> (Hoffman[nsegg], 1804)			NE		
<i>Cupido argiades</i> (Pallas, 1771)			NE		
<i>Cupido decolorata</i> (Staudinger, 1886)			DD		
<i>Cupido minimus</i> (Fuessly, 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC	5	LC
<i>Cupido osiris</i> (Meigen, 1829)		VU B2a	VU B2a		
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Eumedonia eumedon</i> (Esper, [1780])			NE	3	VU
<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i> (Poda, 1761)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU	8	LC
<i>Iolana iolas</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1816)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Kretania sephirus</i> (Fruvaldszky, 1835)			NE	3	VU
<i>Lampides boeticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)			NE	7	LC
<i>Leptotes pirithous</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)			LC		
<i>Lysandra bellargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lysandra coridon</i> (Poda, 1761)			NE	7	LC
<i>Phengaris alcon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU D1D2		
<i>Phengaris arion</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	CR		
<i>Plebejus argus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i> (Bergsträsser, 1779)			NE		
<i>Plebejus idas</i> (Linnaeus 1761)			NE		
<i>Polyommatus admetus</i> (Esper, [1783])			NE		
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i> (Schneider, 1792)			NE	7	LC
<i>Polyommatus aroaniensis lurae</i> Parmentier, Vila <i>et al.</i> , 2022			DD		
<i>Polyommatus aroaniensis orphicus</i> Kolev, 2005			DD		
<i>Polyommatus damon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			LC		
<i>Polyommatus eros</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	CR (A1b)	CR	VU		
<i>Polyommatus escheri</i> (Hübner, [1823])			NE	3	VU
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Polyommatus ripartii</i> (Freyer, 1830)			NT		
<i>Polyommatus thersites</i> (Cantener, 1835)			NE		
<i>Pseudophilotes vicrama</i> (Moore, 1865)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU	8	LC
<i>Scolitantides orion</i> (Pallas, 1771)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Tarucus balkanica</i> (Freyer, [1843])	VU (A1b)	VU B2a	VU B2a		
Theclinae					
<i>Callophrys rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	
<i>Favonius quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU D1D2		
<i>Satyrium acaciae</i> (Fabricius, 1787)			NE	3	VU
<i>Satyrium ilicis</i> (Esper, [1779])			NE	7	LC
<i>Satyrium pruni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	3	VU
<i>Satyrium spini</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE		
<i>Satyrium w-album</i> (Knoch, 1782)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU A1b		
<i>Thecla betulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU A1b	VU A1b		

	Red List (2006)	Red List (2013)	Red List (2022)	Note	Proposed status
Riodinidae					
Riodininae					
<i>Hamearis lucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (B2a)	VU B2a	VU B2a		
Nymphalidae					
Apaturinae					
<i>Apatura ilia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Apatura iris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			VU		
<i>Apatura metis</i> Freyer, 1829			VU		
Charaxinae					
<i>Charaxes jasius</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	LRnt	LRnt	LC		
Danainae					
<i>Danaus chrysippus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	LRnt	LRnt	LC		
Heliconiinae					
<i>Argynnis pandora</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Boloria dia</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)			NE	3	VU
<i>Boloria euphrosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Boloria graeca</i> (Staudinger, 1870)			NE		
<i>Boloria pales</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE	3	VU
<i>Boloria titania</i> (Esper, [1793])			VU		
<i>Brenthis daphne</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE	7	LC
<i>Brenthis hecate</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Brenthis ino</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)			NE	3	VU
<i>Fabriciana adippe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)			NE		
<i>Fabriciana niobe</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			LC		
<i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Speyeria aglaja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
Libytheinae					
<i>Libythea celtis</i> (Laicharting, 1782)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
Limenitidinae					
<i>Limenitis camilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)			VU		
<i>Limenitis reducta</i> Staudinger, 1901	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
Nymphalinae					
<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Euphydryas maturna</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			DD	4	VU
<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Melitaea cinxia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)			VU		
<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, [1778])			NE	7	LC
<i>Melitaea ornata</i> Christoph, 1893			DD		
<i>Melitaea phoebe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Melitaea trivia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Nymphalis xanthomelas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	DD	4	VU
<i>Polygonia c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Polygonia egea</i> (Cramer, [1775])			NE		
<i>Vanessa atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
Satyrinae					
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	3	VU
<i>Arethusana arethusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Brintesia circe</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Chazara briseis</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Coenonympha arcania</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)			NE	7	LC
<i>Coenonympha leander</i> (Esper, [1784])			VU		
<i>Coenonympha orientalis</i> (Rebel, [1910])			VU		
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Coenonympha rhodopensis</i> Elwes, 1900	VU (A1b)	VU	NE		
<i>Erebia aethiops</i> (Esper, 1777)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Erebia albertanus</i> (Prunner, 1798)			NE		
<i>Erebia cassioides</i> (Hohenwarth, 1792)			DD		
<i>Erebia epiphron</i> (Knoch, 1783)			VU		
<i>Erebia euryale</i> (Esper, [1805])			NE		
<i>Erebia gorge</i> (Hübner, [1804])			NT		
<i>Erebia ligea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE		
<i>Erebia medusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU (A1b)	VU	LC		
<i>Erebia melas</i> (Herbst, 1796)	DD		LC		
<i>Erebia oeme</i> (Hübner, [1804])			LC		
<i>Erebia ottomana</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1847]			NE		
<i>Erebia pandrose</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)			NT		
<i>Erebia pronoe</i> (Esper, [1780])	DD		DD		
<i>Erebia rhodopensis</i> Nicholl, 1900			DD		
<i>Erebia triarius</i> (Prunner, 1798)			DD		
<i>Hipparchia fagi</i> (Scopoli, 1763)			LC		
<i>Hipparchia fatua</i> Freyer, [1843]			NE		
<i>Hipparchia semele</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU (A1b)	VU	DD		
<i>Hipparchia senthes</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1908)			DD		
<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		
<i>Hipparchia syriaca</i> (Staudinger, 1871)			NE		
<i>Hipparchia volgensis</i> (Mazochin-Porshnyakov, 1952)			DD		
<i>Hyponephele lupinus</i> (Costa, 1836)			NE		
<i>Hyponephele lycaon</i> (Kühn, 1774)			NE		
<i>Kirinia climene</i> (Esper, [1783])			NE	3	VU
<i>Kirinia roxelana</i> (Cramer, 1777)			NE		
<i>Lasiommata maera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lasiommata megera</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)			NE	7	LC
<i>Lasiommata petropolitana</i> (Fabricius, 1787)			NE	3	VU
<i>Maniola jurtina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Melanargia galathea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Melanargia larissa</i> (Geyer, [1828])			NE	7	LC
<i>Melanargia russiae</i> (Esper, [1783])	CR (B2c)	CR	NE		
<i>Minois dryas</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	VU (A1b)	VU	VU	6	DD
<i>Pararge aegeria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			NE	7	LC
<i>Protorebia phegea</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)			NE		
<i>Pseudochazara amalthea</i> (Frivaldszky, 1845)			VU		
<i>Pseudochazara amymone</i> Brown, 1976			VU		
<i>Pseudochazara geyeri</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846])	VU (A1b)	VU	NT		
<i>Pseudochazara tisiphone</i> Brown, [1981]	VU (A1b)	VU	VU		

Pyronia cecilia (Vallantin, 1894)
Pyronia tithonus (Linnaeus, 1771)
Satyrus ferula (Fabricius, 1793)

Red List (2006)	Red List (2013)	Red List (2022)	Note	Proposed status
		NE		
		NE		
		NE	7	LC

The global coverage map (Fig. 1), featuring all observations from the [Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas](#) (09.i.2025) clearly highlights the expanding survey coverage across the country while also revealing several unexplored areas that require further investigation. Due to the clearly increased distribution of data, both in space and time, we now have a more accurate understanding of the status of many species.

In Table 1, the 'Note' column lists eight classes (1-8), detailing proposed adaptations to the [Red List 2022](#) or confirming significant reclassifications compared to the previous versions (2006 and 2013).

1. Some visually striking butterflies are quickly assigned a higher conservation status, possibly unjustly, compared to what might actually be the case. When considering the status of *P. apollo* and *D. mnemosyne* in light of the [Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas](#) (09.i.2025), questions may arise regarding whether NT truly reflects an accurate assessment.
2. Presumably due to climate change, *P. thrax* has been recorded for the first time ([source](#)) in several locations across Albania. The species is likely to persist in suitable coastal and hot, humid lowland areas, but it is too early to assign a conservation status. As a result, the species is not evaluated (NE).
3. Despite surveys conducted during the optimal flight period, finding new localities for some species has proven difficult. As a result, *Carterocephalus palaemon*, *Pyrgus andromedae*, *Lycaena virgaureae*, *Eumedonia eumedon*, *Kretania sephirus*, *Polyommatus escheri*, *Satyrium acaciae*, *Satyrium pruni*, *Boloria dia*, *Boloria pales*, *Brenthis ino*, *Aphantopus hyperantus*, *Kirinia climene* and *Lasiommata petropolitana* have been assigned the Vulnerable (VU) status. Many of these species are at the limit of their range in Albania and are highly susceptible to local conditions and climate change.
4. Due to the limited recent data, *E. maturna* and *N. xanthomelas* were assigned a DD status in the [Red List 2022](#). However, recent observations have confirmed both species. *E. maturna* was seen again in the same locality, following an initial sighting. In 2023-2024, multiple observations of *N. xanthomelas* were recorded. The latter species tends to emerge suddenly in large numbers, then remain nearly invisible for years. Based on the current evidence, it appears that *N. xanthomelas* is indeed a native species in Albania. Both species are threatened across much of their western range, which is why they have been assigned a Vulnerable status (VU).
5. The recent surveys confirm the reclassification of *Carcharodus alceae*, *Erynnis tages* and *Cupido minimus* to the Least Concern status in the [Red List 2022](#).
6. The recent surveys have failed to reconfirm *Spialia phlomidis* in northern Albania. Were these misidentifications, or is there a significant decline in the North? In southeastern Albania, however, several new localities were discovered, primarily through surveys conducted during the optimal flight period. The proposed status is Vulnerable (VU).
7. Recent surveys have resulted in numerous observations and the discovery of new localities for 45 previously not evaluated species, allowing to be assigned the Least Concern (LC) status.
8. *Minois dryas* has not been recorded in the last decade. The situation is not clear. Were this misidentifications or is there a major decline? The suggested status is Data Deficient (DD).

Fig. 1. Global coverage map incorporating all observations up to the end of 2024, highlighting major underexplored areas (© Sylvain Cuvelier)

Temporal and spatial issues are hindering the timely assessment of threats and determination of conservation status for specific species.

Due to the challenging accessibility of vast areas above the tree line, knowledge of many alpine taxa, including various *Erebia* species, *Pyrgus alveus*, *Pyrgus andromedae*, *Colias caucasica*, ..., remains limited, making it difficult to accurately assess their status. Unfortunately, temporary high-altitude summer shepherd camps are a common practice in Albania, which means they do not guarantee undisturbed nature due to overgrazing. Research on the alpine habitats, which are spread across large parts of Albania, is urgently needed.

Early spring, as highlighted by the recent discovery of *Proterebia phegea* in two disjunct areas ([Verovnik & Verovnik 2022](#); [Prendi et al. 2023](#)), is a period that remains insufficiently studied.

Many species, including *Allanastria cerisyi*, *Zerynthia polyxena*, *Anthocharis damone* and *Anthocharis gruneri* still lack an accurate assessment of their status.

Recently discovered Evolutionarily Significant Units (ESUs) are currently known from a few locations. *Polyommatus aroaniensis lurae* ([Parmentier et al. 2022](#); [Cuvelier 2023](#)) has been documented in the surroundings of Lurë and Voskopojë, while *Pseudochazara tisiphone dibra* ([Cuvelier & Marafi 2025](#)) is known from two isolated areas in Dibër County. Due to the isolated nature of certain Albanian mountain ranges, the discovery of additional ESUs (Evolutionarily Significant Units) remains a possibility. There is also insufficient knowledge regarding the distribution of the Albanian clade of *P. aroaniensis orphicus* ([Parmentier et al. 2022](#); [Cuvelier 2023](#)). To gain a better understanding of their conservation status, comprehensive surveys of suitable intermediate habitats are essential.

Distinguishing certain taxa and cryptic species that closely resemble each other, based on external characteristics, is challenging, even with well-prepared specimens. Accurate identification requires genital dissection and/or DNA barcoding, performed by qualified entomologists. This is the case for some *Pyrgus* sp., *Leptidea sinapis juvernica*, *Pieris napi balcana*, *Melitaea phoebes ornata*, *Hipparchia fagil syriaca* and three species of the subgenus *Parhipparchia*. Since much of the data comes from biodiversity repositories, often supported only by a photo, it is not possible to accurately determine the status of such species. For this moment, AI-driven identification tools are not yet performant in such cases. Recently, a new and ambitious initiative ([InsectAI COST Action](#)) was launched. However, it is possible that such taxa may pose challenges that AI will not be able to address. Nevertheless, it will undoubtedly enhance the quality of data on biodiversity platforms.

M. tessellum, *P. chloridice* and *N. rivularis* have only been reported in historical publications, with limited or unclear data regarding their locations and dates, and have not been recorded in the recent surveys. Although classified as Data Deficient (DD) in the [Red List 2022](#), the scarcity of suitable food plants for the first two species in Albania, combined with the fact that all previous records of *N. rivularis* have been shown to be misidentifications of *Limenitis reducta*, led to their removal from Table 1. This decision was based on the absence of any recent confirmed sightings.

Conclusion

Based on the data presented in [Cuvelier et al. \(2018\)](#), [Cuvelier et al. \(2023\)](#) and the [Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas](#) (version 09.i.2025), this publication offers a new perspective for revising the Red List and advancing butterfly conservation efforts in Albania. It will also guide various strategic directions, helping to define objectives and develop effective plans to achieve them. It is important to acknowledge the inherent limitations of the actual Red List, including data gaps and the challenges of accurately assessing certain species.

A coordinated approach across various action plans is essential to enhance global knowledge of Albanian butterflies, ensuring the precise targeting of species and areas for conservation efforts.

1. Filling the gaps in the distribution data.

The latest global coverage map for Albania still highlights numerous unexplored white areas that require further investigation.

Additionally, many regions above the tree line, critical biotopes for sensitive species and habitats, remain difficult to access. There is significant room for improvement in addressing these altitudinal gaps.

2. Filling temporal gaps in the data.

This update offers a refined overview of many species, but substantial work remains, especially for early-emerging species.

Globally, further research is still needed on adult specimens for many species throughout the entire period from early spring to early autumn across all regions.

3. Developing a new version of Prime Butterfly Areas in Albania.

It involves selecting key sites for conservation and monitoring major taxa and regions.

This process will focus on addressing geographical and temporal gaps to ensure a more comprehensive and effective identification of priority areas.

4. Collecting more objective data on rarer, and difficult to identify taxa, and those at the edge of their distribution range.

They may be common taxa, but protecting those at the edge of their distribution range remains a priority.

Despite challenges in interpretation, modeling studies can help identify unexplored areas that could be vital hotspots for threatened species in need of urgent surveys.

AI tools could enhance the efficiency of existing modeling software, making it a promising option for accelerating research. Testing these advancements in a country with many unexplored regions could significantly improve the knowledge of the Albanian butterfly distribution.

AI could also aid in monitoring species by minimizing bias while maximizing both the quantity and quality of collected data. Due to the recent success of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in other domains and applications, new image-based and AI-assisted tools, alongside traditional methods, are likely to be critical for meeting this information need.

5. Building a targeted conservation program for species for which Albania is the worldwide stronghold.

Developing a specialized program for species where Albania serves as a global stronghold is essential. *Pseudochazara amymone*, *Pseudochazara geyeri*, *Pseudochazara tisiphone*, and *Polymmatatus aroaniensis lurae* are prime candidates for initiating an in-depth study of their populations and ecological dynamics, providing valuable insights for developing effective management strategies to ensure the long-term survival of these taxa.

6. Selecting umbrella species for conservation efforts in Albania.

Selecting umbrella species for conservation efforts in Albania is crucial. Certain taxa, admired for their beauty or unique ecology, such as *Parnassius apollo*, *Phengaris arion*, and *Phengaris alcon*, can play a key role in habitat protection. These species attract attention and support, making them valuable components of action plans aimed at safeguarding Albania's biodiversity.

7. Selecting monitoring routes.

The chosen routes will be surveyed three times per year and consistently monitored over multiple years. This long-term approach will help assess overall butterfly populations, track changes in specific species, and evaluate how these areas and their biodiversity evolve over time.

8. Engaging the Albanian ministry to develop a renewed legal framework through the publication of an updated Red List.

Engaging the Albanian Ministry of Tourism and Environment to develop a renewed legal framework is essential for strengthening the protection of endangered species. Publishing an updated Red List will offer a more accurate, data-driven foundation for focused conservation efforts and legal safeguards. The official status of endangered species, as provided by the Albanian Government in 2013 ([Albania's Biodiversity and Protected Areas. An executive summary](#)), is now outdated and requires revision across all species groups.

There will always be areas requiring improvement, whether through the creation of policies aimed at stabilizing or recovering endangered species or through more intensive research efforts in specific regions. Identifying and prioritizing these areas is crucial for strengthening conservation strategies and ensuring the long-term protection of biodiversity.

Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the conception, analysis, and writing of this work. Each author was involved in all stages of the research process, from conceptualization through data analysis, to drafting and revising the manuscript.

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Supplementary material

The comparison of the three previous Red Lists for the Butterflies of Albania, within the context of the [European Red List](#) (2010), the [Mediterranean Red List](#) (2016), the [Habitat Directives](#), and species with declining, disjunct, and range-limited populations is accessible through [Fluturat e Shqipërisë](#) online.

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